

**Parliamentary Work and Pension Committee Call for Evidence
Transition to State Pension Age**

Response from the

NIHR Policy Research Unit in Healthy Ageing

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The NIHR Policy Research Unit in Healthy Ageing

The National Institute for Health and Care Research (NIHR) Policy Research Unit in Healthy Ageing 2024 – 2028 (HAPRU – formerly NIHR PRU Older People and Frailty) has been funded since January 2019 by the NIHR to work directly with the Department of Health and Social Care (DHSC) and its arm's-length bodies. HAPRU is a collaboration between the University of Manchester, Newcastle University and the London School of Economics. HAPRU is a long-term resource for policy research and rapid-response service, providing evidence for emerging policy and practice. The team also provides expert advice to policy makers, senior civil servants and analysts on the evidence base and options for policy development. For further information on the HAPRU and to view our current and past research see our website www.hapru.nihr.ac.uk . Please note, not all the work of the PRU is in the public domain, therefore please contact us if you would like to discuss anything detailed below, on our website, or of relevance to the work you are doing in relation to healthy ageing. We would be very happy to speak with you.

Structure of Response

The following submission provides a high-level response to the Parliamentary Work and Pensions Committee Call for Evidence on Transitions to State Pension Age. It is deliberately brief and specific in its response, describing a programme of work HAPRU have delivered over the past 18 months in relation to longer working lives - exploring the impact of changes in state pension age on health and wellbeing (see webpage for further information [NIHR Policy Research Unit in Healthy Ageing | Longer working lives](#)).

We have identified the key questions from the inquiry and responded to these collectively. Our response includes research which has been completed as part of our longer working lives programme and includes an international review and quantitative analysis. Please note, this is currently unpublished research and is purposefully high level so as not to present any barriers to future academic publication.

Key inquiry questions of relevance

The research directly addresses the question on impact assessment in the call for evidence, and can also provide some data on the characteristics of the cohort:

Question - What do we know about the expected impact of the increase in the State Pension age from 66 to 67, for example, by income decile and protected characteristic?

Question - Are there particular characteristics of the 60 to 66 age group to take account of in assessing how policies support the transition to pension age?

A short summary of the research follows, with more detailed executive summaries attached as Appendix A (The impact of changes in state pension age on health and economic outcomes: a rapid review) and Appendix B (The impact of rising state pension age on health and well-being

outcomes of people aged 50+: a quantitative analysis investigating rises in SPA for women)

Summary

The context

The UK State Pension Age (SPA) has risen from 60 to 66 for women, with further increases planned. This change aims to enhance the sustainability of the pension system and encourage longer working lives. This research aimed to identify the likely impacts on health, well-being and unpaid care, how these varied by socioeconomic position.

Our approach

1. A rapid review of published evidence was undertaken to understand the impact of changes in the state pension age on health and unpaid care outcomes. Extensive searches were used to identify relevant evidence.
2. We analysed data from 12 waves (2009–2022) of the UK Household Longitudinal Study (Understanding Society), focusing on women born between 1949 and 1955 who had been in paid employment. Four outcomes were considered: mental well-being, mental functioning, physical functioning, and provision of unpaid care. Analyses controlled for socio-demographic characteristics and job type.

Key findings from our review of the international literature

- Published evidence is available on the health and unpaid care impact over eight reforms (dating between 1967-2011) in six countries (France, Germany, Israel, Italy, Spain, UK).
- International evidence suggests that across six reforms, delaying the age at which people can claim a pension was associated with poor physical and mental health, but mostly for disadvantaged groups. Changes in the pension age appeared to have little or no adverse impact on health for more advantaged populations, or those in jobs with lower physical and psychological burden or more control over tasks. However, diverse political, economic and socio-cultural contexts mean that caution is needed in extrapolating non-UK findings to the UK context.
- In the UK, the 1995 and 2011 pension reforms adversely affected the psychological wellbeing, and mental and physical health of women disadvantaged by socioeconomic status and high job strain, and women without a partner. The reforms were also linked to a reduction in hours of unpaid care by older women.

Key findings from our empirical work (analyses of Understanding Society)

- On average, increases in SPA were associated with improvements in well-being and mental functioning. There was no effect on physical functioning or on provision of unpaid care.

- Although the subgroup analyses did not produce definitive results, statistically significant effects were observed in some groups, particularly among women in managerial or professional roles.
- Gains in well-being and mental functioning were most pronounced in cohorts facing the largest rises in SPA, especially women born in 1953/54. Improvements peaked at around seven years, and then diminished, becoming insignificant by nine to ten years
- When examining the pathway from policy change to the change in well-being, the results cannot confirm the hypothesis that the difference in well-being is due (at least in part) to the longer working lives amongst women affected by the policy.

Implications

Our findings suggest that previous rises in the state pension age may have had differential impacts across socioeconomic groups. In particular, women in managerial or professional roles appear more likely to experience neutral or positive effects on wellbeing and mental health following increases in the SPA. Policymakers should also consider wider factors such as financial security, retirement planning and support during the transition to pension eligibility. Targeted measures are needed for disadvantaged groups, particularly those in physically demanding or low-control jobs, to help prevent widening health inequalities.

Appendix One

The impact of changes in state pension age on health and economic outcomes: a rapid review

Executive Summary

Background

The UK State Pension Age (SPA) has risen in recent years to 66 for men and women. A further rise to 67 is planned for men and women between 2026 and 2028.¹ This rise in SPA is expected to be accompanied by an increase in the number of people in the workforce and may have implications for health, health inequalities, and the supply of unpaid care. Enhancing our understanding of these issues can inform policy efforts to support populations most exposed to any adverse impacts of prolonged working.

Aims

This review aimed to address the following question: What is known about the impact of changes in the state or mandatory pension age on health, wellbeing, and economic outcomes?

As part of this, we also wanted to understand:

- a. What is known about how the impact of changes in the state or mandatory pension age vary by subgroups (including, but not limited to, age, sex, ethnicity, socioeconomic position, geographic location, and unpaid carer status)?
- b. What study designs are used to identify the causal effects of changes in the state or mandatory pension age on a range of outcomes?

Methods

Rapid systematic review methods were used.²

Criteria

Broadly, studies were sought from any country where a change in the state pension age was made. A change to state pension age was considered an eligible reform if the pension was a non-contributory or contributory basic pension from public finances, or a mandated public pension plan. Eligible studies reported evidence about the impact of a planned or actual change in the age at which a population becomes eligible for a state pension on a range of health, wellbeing and economic outcomes. Studies reporting projections of outcomes were also eligible for inclusion in the review. Evaluations must include a rise in the state pension age as an explicit part of the methodological design. A change in the state pension age is considered planned if dates for the reform are given. Pension reforms from any country were eligible; no restrictions on publication language were imposed. No date limits were applied, and both quantitative and qualitative evaluative study designs were eligible.

Search Strategy

A search strategy was designed, piloted and refined by an experienced information specialist. Searches were conducted in four electronic databases, grey literature sources and through requests via our networks. Searches were conducted in May 2024 and updated in May 2025. To identify emerging evidence, we searched for ongoing studies from UK funders.

Study selection, quality assessment and synthesis

Titles and abstracts were screened for relevance. The full texts of selected records were retrieved and assessed against the review criteria. Both stages of screening were undertaken independently by two researchers and disagreements resolved through discussion or consensus with a third person. Study quality was assessed using an adapted version of the Critical Appraisal Skills Checklist for Cohort Studies (CASP). A narrative synthesis summarised evidence about the impact of changes in the state pension age on health and unpaid care outcomes. Evidence about the impact on economic outcomes was mapped in a summary table.

Findings

After screening, 16 studies (18 publications) reported evidence about the impact of changing the state pension age on health or unpaid care outcomes: these formed the basis of our narrative synthesis. Eight reforms across six countries (France, Germany, Israel, Italy, Spain, the UK) are represented in these studies. Studies from the UK and Italy report evidence relating to two pension reforms.

Executive Summary Table 1 summarises the headline findings from each reform. Across the UK, Spain, Italy, Germany and Israel (seven reforms), there was evidence that delaying the age at which people can claim a pension was linked to poor health, particularly for groups disadvantaged by low income, routine occupations, high demand and low-self value jobs, and with previous poor health.

Executive Summary Table 1. Summary of health and unpaid care impact across all reforms

Reform	Number of studies	Summary of health impact	Summary of mortality impact	Summary of unpaid care impact
France, 1993	1	-	No clear evidence of an impact of pension reform on mortality. No clear pattern by wage or sex.	-
Germany, 1999	3	Adverse impact on mental health, diabetes, obesity, spine and back conditions, musculoskeletal conditions, connective tissue disorders (not cardiovascular), and health service use. Mixed impact on health costs. No impact on disability pension.	-	-
Israel, 2004	1	Pension reform linked to poorer health on some outcomes. An increase in morbidity was demonstrated but only in comparison to a younger cohort. No strong	-	-

		evidence that impact differed by years of schooling.		
Italy, 1992, 2012	3	Pension reforms linked to poor mental health outcomes in some but not all age cohorts; evidence for physical health outcomes inconsistent. No consistent pattern by education and occupation; a greater risk of claiming disability benefits and taking sick leave observed for those in poorer health on lower incomes.	-	-
Spain, 1967	1	-	Pension reform linked to greater risk of mortality, particularly for men and those employed in industries where workers feel undervalued.	-
UK, 1995, 2011	7	Pension reform linked to psychological distress, and poorer mental and physical health for women in lower occupational groups, working in high demand jobs, and without partners.	-	Pension reforms linked to a reduction in unpaid caregiving.

Poor health outcomes linked to delayed pensions in studies evaluating these reforms were: mental health (measured by the MCS of the SF-12); psychological distress; anxiety; physical health (measured by the PCS of the SF-12); hospitalisations; physician visits; healthcare expenditures; BMI; smoking; grip strength; increased prevalence of various conditions; morbidity (measured by a Morbidity Index); poor health (measured by a Poor Health Index); self-reported sickness and disability (not further defined); claiming a disability pension and using sick days.

For the 1993 reform in France, there was no evidence of an impact on mortality, which was the only health outcome considered in the study evaluation.

A reduction in unpaid care was also linked to the UK pension reforms in one study.

Discussion

This rapid review aimed to summarise evidence about the impacts of reforms to state pension ages on a range of outcomes. The overall trend in the evidence indicates that extensions to the state pension age are linked with poor health for the most disadvantaged. In the UK evidence, people

who were more advantaged and in jobs with less burden and more control appear to be protected from these adverse impacts. Working longer was also associated with a reduction in the amount of unpaid care, a critical source of support for many older people in the UK.

These findings have three key implications. First, the disproportionate impact on the least advantaged suggests that extending the state pension age in the UK has the potential to widen health inequalities. Second, there was evidence that workers who feel valued or who were employed in jobs with less physical and psychological burden appear to be protected from the adverse effects of prolonged working. Action to avoid any adverse health impacts of a rise in the pension age in the UK may need to consider the nature and conditions of people's employment earlier in the life course. Finally, any reduction of unpaid care provided by populations exposed to the UK reforms has implications for social care in England.

Gaps in evidence for the UK

Key gaps identified in the UK evidence, which may inform our empirical analyses, included consideration of:

- The impact on measures of activities of daily living (ADL) and Instrumental ADL (IADL) disability.
- Mortality
- The socioeconomic patterns in the health impact of SPA changes by considering other dimensions of disadvantage, such as measures of accumulated wealth (e.g. income and assets).

Strengths and limitations

Our searches of both published and grey literature, in English and other languages, have ensured a comprehensive capture of global evidence for this review. This is a major strength of our work. We chose to consider international evidence from reforms in any country, to maximise the data available. However, the political, socio-cultural, health and economic contexts of these reforms inevitably vary, as do the time periods in which they took place. Context plays a key role in the outcomes of policy interventions, which limits the parallels we can draw to the impact of the UK pension reform. We would therefore advise a degree of caution in drawing too heavily on the non-UK evidence when considering implications for health policy in England. We also included both direct and proxy measures of health, which allowed us to maximise the evidence available to synthesise. However, two proxy measures of health in particular should be interpreted with caution: claiming a disability pension or disability benefits and sick days from work. Entry into a disability pension (or take up of disability benefits) is more likely to represent a substitute effect of a delayed pension, rather than deteriorating health from longer working. Also, sick days from work are more likely to be reported by people employed in occupations with more generous sick leave entitlement. As such, a measure of sick days may not be an accurate measure of the health of the broader population. Other measures of health identified in the review evidence, such as the GHQ, are validated and offer a reliable picture of the health impact of delaying the state pension age.

Conclusion

Delaying the age at which people can claim a state pension is linked to poor health outcomes. This impact is not uniform across populations, with the most disadvantaged groups more likely to experience declines in and risks to their health. Job quality, measured by the degree of burden and control experienced and how valued workers feel, may be a protective factor alongside higher socioeconomic status. Longer working from delaying the pension age may also lead to a reduction

in unpaid care by women in later life. Evidence from this review suggests that extending the SPA has potential implications for policy measures to reduce health inequalities and meet social care need among older populations.

References

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Appendix Two

The impact of rising state pension age on health and well-being outcomes of people aged 50+: a quantitative analysis investigating rises in SPA for women.

Executive Summary

Background

The UK State Pension Age (SPA) has undergone substantial reforms in recent decades. For many years, women became eligible for the state pension at age 60 and men at 65. The Pensions Act 1995 began a process to equalise SPA for men and women. The plan was to raise women's SPA to 65 by 2020, but under the 2011 Pensions Act the new qualifying age of 65 for women was brought forward to 2018. Subsequent legislation increased SPA further for both men and women, with the rise from 65 to 66 implemented between December 2018 and October 2020. A further rise to 67 is scheduled between 2026 and 2028, and proposals to increase to 68 are under consideration. These changes aim to ensure the financial sustainability and intergenerational fairness of the state pension system in light of an ageing population and increasing longevity, while encouraging older adults to remain in the workforce for longer. However, the implications of such reforms extend beyond fiscal considerations. The requirement to work longer before receiving a state pension may have complex and uneven effects on health and well-being. Extended working lives can confer benefits for some, through financial security, daily structure, social interaction, and mental stimulation, but may harm others, particularly those in poor health or in physically demanding, low-control jobs. The health effects are likely to be socially patterned, potentially widening inequalities if disadvantaged groups bear disproportionate burdens. Despite extensive research on work, retirement and health, relatively little evidence assesses the effects of policy-driven SPA increases. Existing studies suggest such reforms may affect subgroups differently. The aim of this study is to examine how rising SPA affects health, well-being and unpaid care among older women experiencing extended working lives.

Methods

This study uses longitudinal data from the first 12 waves (2009–2022) of Understanding Society, the UK Household Longitudinal Study. The dataset provides rich information on employment status, occupation, health and well-being, and demographic characteristics for UK households, allowing us to follow individuals over time. Our analytical sample included women born between 1949 and 1955 who are or had previously been in paid employment, excluding those never in paid work or providing proxy responses. Women born in 1949 were considered the control group. We defined 'treatment' as the period from age 60 onwards for women affected by the SPA reform (those born in 1950 to 1955), representing the point at which they would have been eligible for the pension under previous rules but were no longer so. We employed a heterogeneous difference-in-differences (DiD) approach with regression adjustment (RA) estimators, following Callaway and Sant'Anna (2021). This method compares how an outcome changes for each of the post-policy cohorts (1950/51 – 1955/56) at each time point compared to the unaffected pre-policy cohort (1949) at each corresponding time and controlling for covariates. It allows for variation in treatment timing between cohorts and adjusts for differences in covariates, improving robustness over standard DiD designs. Two models were estimated: Model 1 controlled for marital status, education, and number of children, while Model 2 additionally adjusted for job type (management

and professional, intermediate, routine). The outcomes examined were: GHQ-12 scores (lower values indicating better well-being), SF-12 Mental Component Score (MCS) for mental functioning, and SF-12 Physical Component Score (PCS) for physical functioning, and provision of unpaid care. We estimated Average Treatment Effects on the Treated (ATETs) aggregated across cohorts, across time points, and by treatment exposure duration. Subgroup analyses examined whether impacts varied by most recent job type, and robustness checks used a placebo sample of men unaffected by the reform to rule out confounding by broader time trends. To explore potential mediation mechanisms, we also estimated a generalised structural equation model (GSEM) to assess whether changes in employment status helped to explain the reform's effects on well-being. This allowed us to examine both direct effects of the SPA increase and any indirect effects operating through employment, using a logit model for the mediator and a linear model for GHQ with bootstrap standard errors.

Findings

The SPA increase was associated with statistically significant improvements in mental well-being and mental functioning outcomes when compared to the unaffected pre-policy cohort. Specifically, these policy effects were driven primarily by the 1952/53 and 1953/54 birth cohorts. No significant effect was found for physical functioning, as measured by SF-12 PCS or for the provision of unpaid care. Cohort-level analyses showed that improvements were concentrated in those experiencing the largest SPA increases, notably women born in 1953/54, who faced an accelerated rise in SPA due to the introduction of a second reform partway through the period between their 60th birthday and their SPA as prescribed by the first reform. When examining outcomes by treatment exposure duration, effects on well-being and mental health functioning emerged approximately two years after treatment, peaked at around 67 years old, and declined to non-significance by age 69 and 70. This temporal pattern suggests that improvements may be linked both to continued employment and to the transition into retirement itself, which previous literature associates with a 'honeymoon effect'.

We tested this statistically with a GSEM approach. The mediation analysis found no evidence that being employed significantly explained the observed higher well-being. Although affected women were more likely to remain in work longer, this does not appear to translate into an effect on GHQ, indicating that the reform's impact on well-being were not significantly driven by employment changes. Subgroup analysis proved inconclusive. Despite significant treatment effects for women in management and professional occupations, similar trends were observed for women in lower-reward occupations, but sample sizes limited the statistical power of our subgroup analysis. Using an unaffected male sample, including men born between April 1949 and November 1953 who were unaffected by the reform, we performed robustness analysis. Results showed no significant changes in any outcome measures, lending credibility to the causal interpretation of our primary analysis.

Interpretation

Our findings support the idea that prolonged employment has some positive impacts and challenge the assumption that a policy increasing SPA harms women's mental health on aggregate. For many women affected by the policy, particularly those born in 1952/53 and 1953/54, the raised SPA was associated with modest improvements in well-being and mental functioning compared to those born in 1949/50 (who reached their SPA at age 60). These gains may arise from several mechanisms

that would need to be explored further, including financial security, social interaction, as well as positive anticipation of pension receipt. Although subgroup analysis proved inconclusive due to limited predicting power, it is important to acknowledge that the literature emphasises the need to examine distributional impacts when evaluating SPA reforms, as average effects can mask important disparities between subgroups. That the mediation analysis did not confirm that staying in employment for longer explained the higher level of wellbeing of those affected by the reform compared with those not affected by it, suggests that policymakers should also consider wider factors such as financial security, retirement planning and support during the transition to state pension eligibility.

Conclusions

The UK's reform of the raising SPA for women was on average associated, with modest improvements in well-being and mental functioning, for women affected by the reform in comparison with an earlier cohort of women. No significant differences in physical functioning were observed. The positive impacts on well-being and mental functionality were largely confined to those in the 1952/53 and 1953/54 birth cohorts, suggesting unequal benefits across the workforce. These findings are important for policymakers considering further SPA increases, as they demonstrate both potential benefits and risks. Without targeted interventions, reforms may exacerbate inequalities.

Implications for policy

Policy responses to SPA increases should be sensitive to their unequal effects. Support mechanisms such as workplace policies, flexible working arrangements, workplace adaptations or retraining programmes may help people in more physically demanding or lower-control jobs to work longer and ameliorate adverse impacts on their health and wellbeing. Whilst opportunities to support retraining and upskilling routes such as returnerships and adult apprenticeships may support older workers re-entry to the employment market. Complementary measures should protect individuals who are unable to extend their working lives due to health problems, caregiving responsibilities, or limited access to suitable employment. These could include targeted financial support or alternative routes to pension eligibility. Future research should focus on understanding the heterogeneity of effects across socio-economic and occupational groups, incorporating measures of job quality, working conditions, and broader life circumstances. By doing so, policymakers can design SPA reforms that promote equity as well as sustainability.